

Game-Based Instructional Delivery in Promoting School Achievement in Public Elementary Schools

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ABSTRACT: The study determined the practices of teachers in developing game-based instruction towards game-based learning, game-based learning activities and game-based learning environment and assessed the school achievement through teachers' performance that includes strategies, innovation and intervention and students' performance which includes motivation, skills and academic achievement. The researcher applied the descriptive method of research where the respondents described the existing practices in line with the Game-Based Instructional Delivery and School Achievement. The descriptions were obtained from her respondents which included One Hundred (100) Public Elementary School Teachers of Tiaong I District Tiaong, Quezon. Survey and type questionnaires were developed and validated to gather data. The result shows that teachers perceived Game-Based Learning as always practiced with mean of 4.13. The teachers assist the students in acquiring their skills. The result shows that teachers perceived Game-Based Learning Activities as always practiced with mean of 4.14. They always practicing and promote positive attitude and sense of fairness and sharing towards the students' mastery. Based on the result, teachers perceived Game-Based Learning Environment as highly-practiced with mean of 4.23. As they go along in teaching their students on various games, the lesson become more enjoyable as they engage them in different games. Based on data gathered and interpreted in Teachers' Performance, the level of school achievement is Very Good (Mean – 4.19). Based on data gathered and interpreted in Students' Performance, the level of School Achievement is Excellent (mean – 4.29). Because they became motivated in learning the topics through the use of games. As the result shown on that the correlation of Game-Based Instructional Delivery and School Achievement is significant at the 0.01 level. And this result explained that the relationship among Game-Based Instructional Delivery and School Achievement are significantly related. Thus, the null hypothesis indicates that there is no significant relationship between Game-Based Instructional Delivery And School Achievement is rejected.

KEYWORDS: Game-Based Instructional Delivery, Game-Based Learning, Game-Based Learning Activities, Game-Based Learning Environment, School Achievement, Teachers' Performance, Students' Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the aims and goals of Department of Education is to develop the skills of the learners. To achieve this, planning and making of learning activities are important as it will help the pupils in discovering, acquiring and developing their skills. Learning takes place in different forms. It includes the use of different strategies and tools in delivering the lessons to have an effective teaching and learning process. It also includes activities that are helpful for learning to happen. The use of educational games became part of processes to make learning more enjoyable and effective. Games are activities that involves thinking and making of strategies. It involves tasks that help pupils to enjoy learning. It may develop the ability of the learning in thinking critically, make strategies and solving skills. And as of today, Teachers used Game-Based Learning that involves the use of computers and other activities to make learning fun and enjoyable. According to Sedig (2008), one of the primary advantages of and uses of games is that they can provide intrinsically motivating learning environments. It is important that games can be given or facilitated on both digital and non-digital because some learners do not have access on computers or internet, and still, it will not hinder the delivery of effective learning process. Educational games do not only enhance students' conceptual understanding but also increase their motivation to learn and allow them to have fun while making sense of the learned content (Baek et al., 2015; da Silva Júnior et al., 2021; Franco-Mariscal et al., 2016; Partovi and Raavi, 2019). And in this study, game – based instructional delivery will help the researcher in promoting the school achievement in public elementary schools.

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2. METHOD

The research study used the descriptive correlational research design to determine the perceptions of Game-Based Instructional Delivery in Promoting the School Achievement Public Elementary Schools. The researcher applied the descriptive method of research where the respondents described the existing practices in line with the Game-Based Instructional Delivery and School Achievement. The descriptions were obtained from her respondents which included the Public Elementary School Teachers of Tiaong I District Tiaong, Quezon. A descriptive research design is used for this study. For this study, there were two (2) identified variables, namely: [A] Game-Based Instructional Delivery as to; Game-Based Learning, Game-Based Learning Activities and Game-Based Learning Environment and [B] School Achievement in terms of: Teachers' Performance that includes strategies, innovation and intervention, and Students' Performance which includes motivation, skills and academic achievement.

Likert scale will use to determine the variables, as of combination 100 teacher respondents from different Public Elementary Schools in Tiaong I District Tiaong, Quezon. The respondents of the study are one hundred (100) Public Elementary School Teachers of Tiaong I District Tiaong, Quezon. The study utilized survey questionnaire that includes the game-based instructional delivery in terms of game-based learning, game-based learning activities and game-based learning environment. Also, it included survey questionnaire on the level of school achievement as to teachers' performance in terms of strategies, innovation and intervention and students' performance in terms of motivation, skills, and academic achievement. The researcher asked the permission from the Office of Schools Division Superintendent and Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor for the conduct of the study. Then the researcher distributed the research instrument through google forms. The data from the instrument gathered immediately after the respondents answer the questionnaire. There were three (3) sets of questionnaires: The questionnaires contained the following parts: Part I referred to the personal information of the teacher respondents where it contained their school, age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, position, years in service, and subject taught. Part II dealt with the assessment of practices in Game-Based Instructional Delivery which includes the Game-Based Learning, Game-Based Learning Activities and Game Based Learning Environment using Likert Scale (5 = Highly-Practiced; 4 = Always Practiced; 3 = Moderately Practiced; 2 = Rarely Practiced; 1 = Not Practiced). And for the Part III, it is about the assessment of School Achievement when it comes to Teachers' Performance as to strategies, innovation, and intervention and for Students' Performance as to motivation, skills and academic achievement using Likert Scale (5 = Excellent; 4 = Very Good; 3 = Good; 2 = Fair; 1 = Poor). The questionnaires were validated in three stages: Stage 1 was the adviser's validation. Stage 2 was the panel of experts' validation and the Stage 3 was the pre-testing validation. This stage utilized thirty (30) teachers from other schools of other districts. The results of the pre-test were statistically examined. All stages of validation determined the appropriateness of the content, clarity of the language and correctness of instructions and scales. After revisions were done based on comment, suggestions and corrections, the revised come emerged. The data gathered are organized, tabulated and treated statistically for analysis and interpretation of each result. The descriptive statistics were used by the researcher to describe the response of the teachers in game-based instructional delivery in promoting success in public elementary schools. To determine the relationship between the game-based instructional delivery, and the school achievement among the Public Elementary School Teachers of Tiaong I District, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (Pearson r) were used. Significant relationship was tested at 5% level of significance.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 This study section focuses on teachers' perception in Game-Based Instructional Delivery

Table 1. Teacher Respondents' Perception in Game-Based Instructional Delivery in Terms of Game-Based Learning

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I employ games (puzzle, vocabulary, spelling and others) as a technique for facilitating learning	4.13	0.69	Always Practiced
2. I assist my pupils in acquiring the skills and capabilities in vocabulary and spelling	4.29	0.62	Highly-Practiced
3. I guide my pupils to learn the lesson by utilizing the games using puzzles and others	4.02	0.72	Always Practiced
4. I address the appropriateness of the games (puzzle, vocabulary, spelling and others) on the lesson	4.07	0.71	Always Practiced
5. I employ games (puzzle, vocabulary, spelling and others) as a technique for facilitating learning	4.13	0.69	Always Practiced
Overall	4.13	0.61	Always Practiced

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Highly-Practiced), 3.21-4.20 (Always Practiced), 2.61-3.20 (Moderately Practiced), 1.81-2.60 (Rarely Practiced), 1.00-1.80 (Not Practiced)

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The results indicate that the highest weighted mean of 4.29 with SD of 0.62, which interpreted as highly-practiced has acquired by the statement “I assist my pupils in acquiring the skills and capabilities in vocabulary and spelling. While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.02 and SD of 0.72 which have equivalent verbal interpretation of Always Practiced has acquired by the statement “I guide my pupils to learn the lesson by utilizing the games using puzzles and others.” The overall weighted mean of 4.13 and standard deviation of 0.61 was given by teacher respondents, which is interpreted as Always Practiced on overall practices of game-based learning. This indicates that Game-Based Learning are always practiced and enhanced by the teacher respondents for an effective teaching and learning process.

Table 2. Teacher Respondents’ Perception in Game-Based Instructional Delivery in Terms of Game-Based Learning Activities

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I guide my pupils in expressing their ideas using various games (puzzle, vocabulary, spelling and others)	4.16	0.71	Always Practiced
I discuss the lesson in an interactive way by using different games such as wheel of fortune, spelling bee to ensure that pupils will understand the lesson	4.06	0.69	Always Practiced
I used to acquire the full potentials of learners using various games.	4.04	0.71	Always Practiced
I promote positive attitude and the sense of fairness and sharing among my pupils while learning the topic or lesson.	4.29	0.62	Highly - Practiced
I guide my pupils in developing their motor skills by completing different task of the games provided.	4.16	0.69	Always Practiced
Overall	4.14	0.60	Always Practiced

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Highly-Practiced), 3.21-4.20 (Always Practiced), 2.61-3.20 (Moderately Practiced), 1.81-2.60 (Rarely Practiced), 1.00-1.80 (Not Practiced)

The results indicate that the highest weighted mean of 4.29 and SD of 0.62, which interpreted as highly-practiced has acquired by the statement “I promote positive attitude and the sense of fairness and sharing among my pupils while learning the topic or lesson.” While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.04 and SD of 0.71 which have equivalent verbal interpretation of Always Practiced has acquired by the statement “I used to acquire the full potentials of learners using various games. The overall weighted mean of 4.14 and standard deviation of 0.60 was given by teacher respondents, which is interpreted as Always Practiced on overall practices of game-based learning activities. The overall weighted mean of 4.14 and standard deviation of 0.60 was given by teacher respondents, which is interpreted as Always Practiced on overall practices of game-based learning activities. This indicates Game-Based Learning Activities are always practiced by the teachers that will lead the students to have more acquired skills.

Table 3. Teacher Respondents’ Perception in Game-Based Instructional Delivery in Terms of Game-Based Learning Environment

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I make the lesson more enjoyable for my pupils by engaging their interest in manipulative games	4.19	0.72	Always Practiced
I identify the games that are applicable to the topic that I discuss	4.18	0.74	Always Practiced
I make the classroom safe and create happy environment through the implementation of various game-based strategies.	4.34	0.68	Highly-Practiced
I help my pupils in achieving the competencies to be mastered	4.34	0.65	Highly-Practiced
I apply game-based strategies as an intervention and innovation in the learning process	4.11	0.68	Always Practiced
Overall	4.23	0.62	Highly-Practiced

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Highly-Practiced), 3.21-4.20 (Always Practiced), 2.61-3.20 (Moderately Practiced), 1.81-2.60 (Rarely Practiced), 1.00-1.80 (Not Practiced)

The results indicate that the highest weighted mean of 4.34 with standard deviation of 0.68, which interpreted as highly-practiced has acquired by the statements “I make the classroom safe and create happy environment through the implementation of various game-based strategies,” and “I help my pupils in achieving the competencies to be mastered.” This shows that games are very helpful for the students to be more motivated in learning because of the environment that they have. While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.11 with SD of 0.68 which have equivalent verbal interpretation of Always Practiced has acquired by the statement “I

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apply game-based strategies as an intervention and innovation in the learning process.”. The overall weighted mean of 4.23 was given by teacher respondents, with standard deviation of 0.62 which is interpreted as Highly-Practiced on overall practices of game-based learning environment. This means that Game-based Learning Environment promotes safe and happy classroom environment.

Table 4. Summary Table of Respondents Perception on Game-Based Instructional Delivery

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Game-Based Learning	4.13	0.61	Always Practiced
Game-Based Learning Activities	4.14	0.60	Always Practiced
Game-Based Learning Environment	4.23	0.62	Highly - Practiced
Overall	4.17	0.61	Always Practiced

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Highly-Practiced), 3.21-4.20 (Always Practiced), 2.61-3.20 (Moderately Practiced), 1.81-2.60 (Rarely Practiced), 1.00-1.80 (Not Practiced)

Game-Based Learning achieved the mean of 4.13 and standard deviation of 0.61 with verbal interpretation of Always Practiced indicates that in this factor, the teacher respondents indicates that they assist their students in adopting the skills and capabilities. In Game-Based Learning Activities, the overall mean is 4.14 and standard deviation of 0.60 with verbal interpretation of Always Practiced indicates that the teachers promote positive attitude and sense of fairness and sharing among the students while learning the topic or lessons. And in Game-Based Learning Environment, the mean achieved is 4.23 and standard deviation of 0.62 with verbal interpretation of Highly-Practiced. This indicates that teachers make the classroom safe and they make sure that the students have a happy environment when various games are presented and implemented. And the overall result of Game-Based Instructional Delivery indicates that the implementation of games are use and always practice by the teachers to make sure that there will be an effective teaching and learning process.

3.2 This study section focuses on teachers’ perception in determining the Level of School Achievement in Teachers’ Performance

Table 5. Perceived Level of School Achievement on Teacher’s Performance in Terms of Strategies

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I plan the game that is appropriate for the lesson	4.23	0.72	Excellent
I use games as a strategy to make learning more enjoyable for my pupils	4.22	0.70	Excellent
I guide the pupils in achieving mastery of the lesson	4.29	0.70	Excellent
I provide new learning and experiences to my pupils	4.24	0.68	Excellent
I organized various games that will make teaching-learning process effective	4.07	0.73	Very Good
Overall	4.21	0.65	Excellent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Excellent), 3.21-4.20 (Very Good), 2.61-3.20 (Good), 1.81-2.60 (Fair), 1.00-1.80 (Poor)

The results indicate that the highest weighted mean of 4.29 and standard deviation of 0.70, which interpreted as Excellent has acquired by the statement “I guide the pupils in achieving mastery of the lesson.” While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.07 with standard deviation of 0.73 which have equivalent verbal interpretation of Very Good has acquired by the statement “I organized various games that will make teaching-learning process effective.”. The overall weighted mean of 4.21 with standard deviation of 0.65 was given by teacher respondents, which is interpreted as Excellent .This indicates that the strategies are very helpful for the teachers as the research study of Cheng and Su (2012) stated that the educational games make the learner become the center of learning, which allows the learning process to be easier, more interesting and more effective. Additionally, teaching through games is a holistic strategy that increases classroom participation and student engagement and is more involved in their learning (Higuera-Rodríguez et al., 2021).

Table 6. Perceived Level of School Achievement on Teachers’ Performance in Terms of Innovation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I use games as a new technique in teaching a lesson with my pupils	4.11	0.69	Very Good
I make learning more fun and enjoyable for my pupils	4.28	0.68	Excellent
I make my pupils more active in class during and after the implementation of various games (puzzle, vocabulary, spelling and others)	4.24	0.67	Excellent
I promote the game as an instrument for “independent learning” to my pupils	4.13	0.69	Very Good
It assist me in developing the skills of my pupils	4.18	0.67	Very Good
Overall	4.19	0.62	Very Good

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Excellent), 3.21-4.20 (Very Good), 2.61-3.20 (Good), 1.81-2.60 (Fair), 1.00-1.80 (Poor)

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The results indicate that the highest weighted mean of 4.28 and standard deviation of 0.68, which interpreted as Excellent has acquired by the statement “I make learning more fun and enjoyable for my pupils.” While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.11 which have standard deviation of 0.69 and equivalent verbal interpretation of Very Good has acquired by the statement “I use games as a new technique in teaching a lesson with my pupils.” The overall weighted mean of 4.19 with standard deviation of 0.62 was given by teacher respondents, which is interpreted as Very Good on overall assessment of School Achievement in terms of Teachers’ Performance as to Innovation. This means that teachers use games as innovation in promoting fun and enjoyable learning towards the students’ mastery of the lesson.

Table 7. Perceived Level of School Achievement on Teachers’ Performance in Terms of Intervention

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
I integrate games as part of my intervention to achieve the learning objectives	4.12	0.67	Very Good
I use different games to enhance the knowledge of my pupils	4.12	0.73	Very Good
I develop a positive attitude in my pupils toward learning	4.22	0.66	Excellent
I develop collaboration among my pupils that will result in learning the topics	4.25	0.67	Excellent
I help my pupils in having self-discipline while taking the different games suited to each subject	4.20	0.68	Very Good
Overall	4.18	0.63	Very Good

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (*Excellent*), 3.21-4.20 (*Very Good*), 2.61-3.20 (*Good*), 1.81-2.60 (*Fair*), 1.00-1.80 (*Poor*)

The results indicate that the highest weighted mean of 4.25 and standard deviation of 0.67, which interpreted as Excellent has acquired by the indicator “I develop collaboration among my pupils that will result in learning the topics.” It develop positive attitude towards learning of the students. While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.12 and standard deviation of 0.67 and 0.73 which have equivalent verbal interpretation of Very Good has acquired by the statements I integrate games as part of my intervention to achieve the learning objectives.” and “I use different games to enhance the knowledge of my pupils”. The overall weighted mean of 4.18 with standard deviation of 0.63 was given by teacher respondents, which is interpreted as Very Good on overall assessment of School Achievement in terms of Teachers’ Performance as to Intervention. This means that games are used as an intervention towards the collaborative learning of the students that will lead in achieving teachers’ performance.

3.3 This study section focuses on teachers’ perception in determining the Level of School Achievement in Students’ Performance

Table 8. Perceived Level of School Achievement on Students’ Performance in Terms of Motivation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
They became motivated in the learning process	4.34	0.62	Excellent
They enjoyed playing while learning	4.39	0.62	Excellent
They achieved mastery of the lesson	4.26	0.65	Excellent
They show cooperation, which motivates them to learn the lesson	4.31	0.65	Excellent
They are more focused on the goal to be achieved	4.29	0.67	Excellent
Overall	4.32	0.60	Excellent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (*Excellent*), 3.21-4.20 (*Very Good*), 2.61-3.20 (*Good*), 1.81-2.60 (*Fair*), 1.00-1.80 (*Poor*)

The results indicate that the highest weighted mean of 4.39 and standard deviation of 0.62, which interpreted as Excellent has acquired by the statement “They enjoyed playing while learning.” While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.26 and standard deviation of 0.65 which have equivalent verbal interpretation of Excellent has acquired by the statement “They achieved mastery of the lesson”. The overall weighted mean of 4.32 with standard deviation of 0.60 was given by teacher respondents, which is interpreted as Excellent on overall assessment of School Achievement in terms of Teachers’ Performance as to Motivation and indicates that games as a motivation leads the teachers in guiding the students to be more focused and cooperative during the learning process. To support the result, studies of many educators have considered Game-Based Learning as an educational tool to speed up the academic achievement motivation of elementary school students (Choi, Huang, Jeffrey, & Baek, 2013; Sung, Hwang, Hung & Huang, 2012; Van Eric, 2006).

Table 9. Perceived Level of School Achievement on Students’ Performance in Terms of Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
They developed their skills toward collaborative learning	4.31	0.61	Excellent
They practiced and apply the skills that they have gained.	4.26	0.65	Excellent

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They were more active in class during and after the implementation of various games	4.32	0.62	Excellent
They enhanced their abilities, which will help them understand the lesson easily	4.21	0.62	Excellent
They acquired the needed skills based on the games implemented	4.21	0.66	Excellent
Overall	4.26	0.59	Excellent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Excellent), 3.21-4.20 (Very Good), 2.61-3.20 (Good), 1.81-2.60 (Fair), 1.00-1.80 (Poor)

The results indicate that the highest weighted mean of 4.32 and standard deviation of 0.62, which interpreted as Excellent has acquired by the statement “They were more active in class during and after the implementation of various games While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.21 and standard deviation of 0.62 and 0.66 which have equivalent verbal interpretation of Excellent has acquired by the statements “They enhanced their abilities, which will help them understand the lesson easily”, and “They acquired the needed skills based on the games implemented.” The overall weighted mean of 4.26 with standard deviation of 0.59 was given by teacher respondents, which is interpreted as Excellent on overall assessment of School Achievement in terms of Teachers’ Performance as to Skills. Additionally, according to the study of Yang & Chang, (2013); and Chang et al., (2012), game-based learning provides opportunities to engage and develop students’ higher-order thinking skills through game elements to problem solve, evaluate, analyse and create within the game.

Table 10. Perceived Level of School Achievement on Students’ Performance in Terms of Academic Achievement

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
They achieved mastery of the lesson	4.24	0.61	Excellent
They become more active in participating in the class discussion	4.31	0.60	Excellent
They develop a positive attitude toward learning	4.34	0.59	Excellent
They have self-discipline as part of their study habits	4.25	0.64	Excellent
They have better academic achievement based on their applied skills and knowledge	4.24	0.62	Excellent
Overall	4.28	0.57	Excellent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Excellent), 3.21-4.20 (Very Good), 2.61-3.20 (Good), 1.81-2.60 (Fair), 1.00-1.80 (Poor)

The results indicate that the highest weighted mean of 4.34 and standard deviation of 0.59, which interpreted as Excellent has acquired by the statement “They develop a positive attitude toward learning.” While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.24 with standard deviation of 0.61 which have equivalent verbal interpretation of Excellent has acquired by the statements “They achieved mastery of the lesson”. Another indicator with weighted mean of 4.24 and standard deviation of 0.62 is “They have better academic achievement based on their applied skills and knowledge.” The overall weighted mean of 4.28 and standard deviation of 0.57 was given by the respondents, which is interpreted as Excellent. It was supported by the result of the study of Chang et al., (2012) that it also demonstrated significant increases of achievement with the use of game-based learning for all students, including low performers on the pre-test.

Table 11. Summary Table on the Level of School Achievement

Variables	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Teachers’ Performance			
1. Strategies	4.21	0.65	Excellent
2. Innovation	4.19	0.62	Very Good
3. Intervention	4.18	0.63	Very Good
Overall	4.19	0.63	Very Good
Students’ Performance			
1. Motivation	4.32	0.60	Excellent
2. Skills	4.26	0.59	Excellent
3. Academic Achievement	4.28	0.57	Excellent
Overall	4.29	0.59	Excellent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Excellent), 3.21-4.20 (Very Good), 2.61-3.20 (Good), 1.81-2.60 (Fair), 1.00-1.80 (Poor)

The results indicate that in the teachers’ performance, the highest weighted mean of 4.21 with standard deviation of 0.65, which interpreted as excellent has acquired by the indicators in terms of strategies. While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.18 with standard deviation of 0.63 which have equivalent verbal interpretation of very good has acquired by the indicators in terms of intervention. The overall result of 4.19 with the SD of 0.63 and verbal interpretation of Very Good shows that the teachers are engaging themselves

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in using games as part of their teaching and learning process. In students' performance, the highest weighted mean of 4.32 with standard deviation of 0.60, which interpreted as excellent has acquired by the indicators in terms of motivation. While, the lowest weighted mean of 4.26 with standard deviation of 0.59 which have equivalent verbal interpretation of excellent has acquired by the indicators in terms of skills. In this indicator, the students enhance their abilities to guide them in understanding the lesson easily. The overall result of 4.29 with the standard deviation of 0.63 and verbal interpretation of excellent indicates that motivation, skills and academic achievement promotes the students' performance that leads to school achievement.

Table 12. Summary Table for the Game-Based Instructional Delivery, Teachers' Performance and Students' Performance

Variables	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Game-Based Instructional Delivery	4.17	0.61	Always Practiced
Teachers' Performance	4.19	0.63	Very Good
Students' Performance	4.29	0.59	Excellent
Overall	4.22	0.61	Highly Practiced Excellent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Highly-Practiced/Excellent), 3.21-4.20 (Always Practiced/Very Good), 2.61-3.20 (Moderately Practiced/Good), 1.81-2.60 (Rarely Practiced/Fair), 1.00-1.80 (Not Practiced/Poor)

The result shows that in Game-Based Instructional Delivery the overall mean is 4.17 with standard deviation of 0.61 and verbal interpretation of Always Practiced. It revealed that Game-Based Learning, Game-based Learning Activities and Game-Based Learning Environment are present in the teaching and learning process of the teachers and students. In teachers' performance, the result shows the mean of 4.19 with standard deviation of 0.63 and verbal interpretation of Very Good. This guides the students in achieving the mastery of the lesson. In Students' Performance, the mean is 4.29 with standard deviation of 0.59 with Excellent as its Verbal Interpretation. To summarized, the overall mean of game-based instructional delivery, teachers' and students' performance is 4.22 with standard deviation of 0.61 and verbal interpretation of Highly-Practiced and Excellent revealed that these variables possess positive impact on the teaching and learning process. And this makes game-based instruction effective towards the teachers' and students' performances.

Table 13. Relationship of Game-Based Instructional Delivery and School Achievement in Terms of Teachers' and Students' Performance

GAME-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL DELIVERY	Teachers' Performance			Students' Performance		
	Strategies	Innovation	Intervention	Motivation	Skills	Academic Achievement
1.Game-Based Learning	.688**	.758**	.741**	.636**	.648**	.680**
2.Game-Based Learning Activities	.790**	.833**	.850**	.696**	.748**	.749**
3.Game-Based Learning Environment	.745**	.824**	.800**	.699**	.744**	.735**

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results indicates that in game-based learning as part of game-based instructional delivery, the highest in teachers' performance with correlation of .758** is Innovation which means that in using games in facilitating learning, the lesson become innovative and promotes new techniques of delivery of instruction. The results in game-based learning activities as part of game-based instructional delivery, the highest in teachers' performance with correlation of .850** is Intervention. As Khan et al., (2021) reported that collaborative learning promotes interaction among students during the gameplay, improving their learning performance. And in the students' performance, the highest correlation of .749** is for academic achievement. This implies that the students learned easily when games are integrated in the lesson. And through this, there will be school achievement. In Game-Based Learning Environment, the result in teachers' performance with the highest correlation of .824** is Innovation. On the other hand, in students' performance, the highest correlation of .744** is achieved by the Skills. As the result indicates the correlation of Game-Based Instructional Delivery as to Game-Based Learning, Game-Based Learning Activities and Game-Based Learning Environment between the School Achievement in terms of Teachers' Performance and Students' Performance, Game-Based Instructional Delivery in teaching and learning process is beneficial to the performance of teachers and students.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusion was drawn. There is a significant relationship among Game-Based Instructional Delivery and School Achievement in terms of Teachers' and Students' Performance, the null hypothesis posited in the study is not supported by evidence; thus, it is not sustained.

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Based on the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby suggested: 1. Enhance and develop more games that the teachers can use in the delivery of instruction towards the mastery of the lesson by the students because games enhances the skills of the learners that can guide them to have the mastery of the lesson It will also help the teacher to become more effective facilitator of learning; 2. Trainings about games and its appropriateness for various topics or lessons for elementary can be conducted to guide and assist the teachers in making and utilizing games in the delivery of instruction; 3. Developing other games can be made by the teachers and experts of technology to make learning process more meaningful to the teachers and students. Because through this, the goals and objectives can be achieved for the school achievement; 4. Game-Based Delivery and Instructions needs to have further study in order to assess more of its effectiveness towards teaching and learning process and for more relevance of games in teaching different subject areas.

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